

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B448
Date: 09 May 2009
Take Off: 08:42:38Z
Landing: 13:32:35Z
Flight Time 4h 49m 57s

Campaign: MEVEX Dust Flight 7 & A-Train Comparison
Operating Area: Central Oman low level area 3

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathowers	Directflight	
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Dave Kindred	Met Office	
5	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM	
6	Core Chem / AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
8	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
9	SWS / SHIMS	Martin Glew	Met Office	
10	Wet Neph / CVI / IIR	Andy Wilson	Met Office	
11	MARSS	Rob King	Met Office	
12	Filters	Anne Klaver	University of Paris	
13	Mini-LIDAR	Joss Kent	Met Office	
14	Observer 1	Abdullah O. R. Al Ojaili	DGCA Safety	
15	Observer 2	Dave Membery	Met Office	
16				
17				
18				
19				

Missing Log Sheet	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by ???
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Wet Neph	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
CVI	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
SWS	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
Mini-LIDAR	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	31 Dec 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following avi format video recordings should be available at the BADC in core_processed/faam-video :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_085007_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_092835_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_093055_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_093707_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_100106_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_110106_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_120106_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_093024_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_093700_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_085002_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_092832_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_093027_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_093703_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_100102_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_110102_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_120102_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_085000_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_092829_1hz.avi

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 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_093707_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_100106_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_110106_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_120106_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_093024_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_093700_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_085002_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_092832_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_093027_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_093703_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_100102_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_110102_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_120102_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_085000_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090509_r0_b448_092829_1hz.avi

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B448
 Date: 9th May 2009
 Project: MEVEX
 Location: Oman

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
083122		Start-Up	0.28 kft	267	Muscat
083516		taxy	0.28 kft	267	start
083730	083938	pirouette	0.28 kft	065	
083959		ASP	0.28 kft	097	closed
084238		T/O	3.4 kft	322	
084902		jw	9.5 kft	215	zero
085016		Video	11.6 kft	210	start FFC, RFC, DFC
090402		!	26.0 kft	208	level FL260
090428		TWC	26.0 kft	208	evap2 on
090516		bbr	26.0 kft	239	retract
090607		GE	26.0 kft	247	max cool
092201	093442	Run 1.1	26.0 kft	169	
092201		Sonde 01	26.0 kft	169	tape attached to parachute
092507		Sonde 02	26.0 kft	161	unchanged sonde
092851		Video	26.0 kft	165	stop/start rec
093022		pt B	26.0 kft	163	
093432		Video	26.0 kft	163	restart
093705		Video	26.0 kft	309	restart
093905		Heimann	26.0 kft	004	cal
094247	095819	Run 1.2	26.0 kft	345	
094247		sonde 03	26.9 kft	345	tape attached to parachute
094600		Sonde 04	26.0 kft	344	unchanged sonde
094716		!	26.0 kft	344	overpass time
095149		pt A	26.0 kft	343	
095930	100824	Profile 1	26.0 - 16.2 kft	160	start at pt B
100114		Video	23.3 kft	164	restart
100130		!	22.8 kft	164	now 1000fpm
101026	102301	Profile 1	16.2 - 8.2 kft	333	
102158		pt A	8.8 kft	347	
102556	103840	Run 2.1	8.2 kft	180	
102728		pt A	8.2 kft	171	
104028	105233	Run 2.2	8.2 - 8.1 kft	324	
105233	105454	Profile 2	8.1 - 6.2 kft	344	
105645	105844	Profile 2	6.2 - 4.2 kft	165	
105852	111037	Run 3.1	4.1 kft	161	stp at b
111111	111240	Profile 3	4.3 - 2.9 kft	122	
111443	111700	Profile 3	2.8 - 1.4 kft	325	
111701	112938	Run 4.1	1.4 kft	336	stop at A

113035	113151	Orbit 1	2.1 - 2.0 kft	026	
113222	113311	Orbit 2	2.0 - 2.1 kft	075	abandoned
113425	114635	Run 4.2	1.3 - 1.4 kft	160	
114729	114846	Orbit 2	2.0 - 1.9 kft	139	
115110	120406	Run 4.3	1.4 - 1.3 kft	349	start at B
120547	121620	Profile 4	1.5 - 15.7 kft	166	
121626	121952	Profile 5	15.8 - 12.2 kft	166	
121952	123130	Run 5.1	12.2 kft	352	
123333	123532	Profile 6	12.2 - 15.0 kft	184	
123532	124253	Run 6.1	15.0 kft	174	
124437	124855	Profile 7	15.1 - 21.0 kft	017	
133235		Land	0.32 kft	176	
133345		ASP	0.32 kft	176	
133851	134043	pirouette	0.32 kft	242	
134441		Shutdown	0.32 kft	266	23 35.36N 58 17.66E
134454		!	0.32 kft	266	ENDEX

B448 06:48:46-13:46:27

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

Pilot: Cpt Luc Lathouwers

NavData Cycle 2009-4 Expires: Thursday, 07 May 2009.

Scale: 1:1301188 (1 inch = 17.85 naut mi). Printed on 08 May 2009

5 4 7 7 4 9 4 6

FliteStar 9.4.5.0

ARIES / MARSS / MODIS / CALIPSO

MEVEX - 'A' train satellite comparison / mod-heavy aerosol loading model comparison

B448

Date: 9th May 2009

Mission Scientist: Dave Kindred

1245 L T/O
1715 L Land

T/O OOMS: 08:45Z (12:45 local)
Land OOMS: 12:57Z (16:57 local)

Location: Central Oman low level area 3
A: 21°30'N 56°00'E B: 20°45'N 56°15'E

No SESITS
(over land)
M/SU seat (T/O classing)

Coordinating with 'A' train satellite overpass at 09:47Z

Weather: Cloud free conditions, mod-high aerosol loadings

Sortie Aim: To validate 'A' train satellite retrievals and forecasts of moderate aerosol conditions.

Key Instruments: ARIES, MARSS, SWS/SHIMS, IR Cameras, Mini Lidar, Small particulate probes, AVAPS, Nephs

Sorted
Items

Sortie profile: MicroTops PRE-FLIGHT

Detail	Item time	Running time	Local time
0 Perform pirouette before take-off			
1 Take off OOMS		08:45:00	12:45:00
2 Transit to operating area at FL260	00:40:00	09:25:00	13:25:00
3 Fly 2 straight and level runs at FL260 between points A and B, dropping 2 sondes on each run	00:20:00	09:45:00	13:45:00
4 Profile descent, from A to B, to FL150 or other suitable level	00:10:00	09:55:00	13:55:00
5 2 Straight and level runs at FL150 B→A A→B (extended)	00:30:00	10:25:00	14:25:00
6 Profile descent to 8000ft or other suitable level B→A	00:07:00	10:32:00	14:32:00
7 Continue straight and level run at 8000ft to A	00:10:00	10:42:00	14:42:00
8 Straight and level run at 8000ft A to B	00:15:00	10:57:00	14:57:00
9 Profile descent to 1000ft B→A	00:10:00	11:07:00	15:07:00
10 Continue straight and level run at 1000ft to A	00:05:00	11:12:00	15:12:00
11 Perform 3 SLRs at 1000ft to arrive back at B	00:45:00	11:57:00	15:57:00
12 Profile ascent to transit alt between B and A	00:20:00	12:17:00	16:17:00
13 Transit back to OOMS or 210	00:40:00	12:57:00	16:57:00
14 Perform pirouette after landing			
Total sortie time		04:12:00	04:12:00

(over Pso 1349L)
1347L
o/h time
(during 2nd)

Solar Azimuth Angle

Keep warm & keep running until on ground

SWS / ARIES - Match sensors with viewing L.

Generally look at dust low level look ↓ as well as ↑ Coordinate AS UNCLE.

MEVEX
DUST/AEROSOL FLIGHT
AREA 3 - CENTRAL OMAN.

Mission Scientist's Log

FL260 =
5000 m
6000 m

Flight No **B448** Date **9-5-09** Name **D.R. Kinoshita** Page **1** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0835					off chocs, BAT 24. MISCAT; START TAXI.
0837		out ground.	060°		START PIROUETTE ↓
0840			060°		END "
* 0842					T/O MISCAT. Clear skies
		WIND N 17, moderate			Mod dust loading near surface.
0850		PASSING FL260			Viso only ~ top of dust/aerosol layer
0852		Mixing v. warm on ground - double bounce			Should cool down a
					transit (be fully functional hereafter)
085730	climb out MISCAT	21,400'	207°		climb out of MISCAT
					Mod - 2 near surface layers (500', 3000-3500' up to 300+ m ⁻¹ counts)
					& another layer @ 5,500' (peak ~ 1500 m ⁻¹)
					slowly ↓ to almost zero (10) by FL200
~ 090345	605 CLIMB	FL260	208°		Now at transit alt. & turning ↓ to head to operating area.
0918	CAMERA				(Mod & LW both not on, trying to bring them back to full functionality now with colder temps. New attempt too cold may work at Mod ht/temps)
092201	START R1.1/2 #1	FL260	177°		Release #1 Released Start R1 A → B (At Point A)
092507	2nd #2.	FL260	162°		Release #2 Released 3 mins into run
					SKY CLEAR IN OBS AREA.
093022					O/H Pt B, continuing beyond on this leg
093442	END R1.1	FL260			END R1.1 at B (extended) & turning ↑
094247	START R1.2	FL260	345°		START R1.2 at B (towards A)
094600	2nd #4	FL260	344°		SAT 'A' TRANS OBS PASS V. SEEN (1 MIN FROM NOW)

ALL 4 SERIES GOOD DATA

Mission Scientist's Log

8000' (x2)
4000' (x1/2)
1200'
800' (x2)

Flight No **B448** Date 9-5-09 Name DK Page 2 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
095149	1-2	FL260	343°		on top Pt 'A' now. Turning slowly ↓.
095500			→		Continue at this height for CO cal
		First level			We'll walk 15 ~ FL100
095930	Profile P1 ↓	FL260	155°		P1 descent at 7000'/min to FL100
095930	Overhead Pt A				but then 1000'/min FL230 ↓ FL100
100125			→		P1 descent rate reduced to 500'/min
100824	P1 interrupt	FL160			P1 interrupt at Pt B, turn S
101026	become P1 ↓	FL160	322°		Descending to FL090 now. (9000'.)
[SUS:]	Will perform orbits extended				1-10 - Sun Leg XT 1200'
					Area of interest 12000' ↓ 9000' for Aerosol (FROM LIDAR)
101740	P1 ↓	FL110	344°		Neph ↑ increase @ this level This layer 1000' 10500'
					lidar - under layer below descending now to 8000 FT on P1 ↓
1021	O/H				O/H Pt A, extending
102301	P1	8000'			END P1 at A (extended)
102556	START 2.1				START R2.1 into 'highest' aerosol / dust Some str turbulence here.
102728	O/H A	8000'	166°		WIND 355° / 10 kT START FILTER SAMPLING
102840	R2.1	8000'			Neph ~ 150 m ⁻¹ ; good STRUCTURE (little separation)
103403	R2.1	8000'	163°		TRAIL FOR AEROSOL / DUST TO BE THINKING AS GOING A → B (ie SWINGS)
103550	R2.1				Neph 100-140 m ⁻¹ now
103840	R2.1	8000'			END RUN AT B; Turn ↑ & REPEAT RUN AT THIS LEVEL
104028	START R2.2	8000'	322°		START Run 2.2 B → A repeat (highest loading here, I think!) at this ht.

Mission Scientist's Log

[Max Neph 240 m⁻¹ at 'A' and 8000']

ALICE ↓
220kt 50° ALICE ↑ 0

Flight No **B 448** Date 9-5-09 Name DK Page 3 of 5 ↓

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
105120	R2.2	8000'	346		More Aerosol/Dust at A end of run confirmed
		Wind 005°/12kt.			
105233	END P2.1	(continuing N)			END R2.2, Start P2 ↓ 4000' (turning at 6000')
105454	START P2.1				Turning 5 & will head back → A 600' → 4000'.
105645	Restart P2	6000'	167°		RECONFIRM P2, 1000'/mi
105844	END P2 START P3	4000'	163°		END P2 at 4000', Start R3.1 A → B
					CAMERAS LW - OK now MW - not perfect, but serviceable.
					MASSS ✓ OK now
110535					Aerosol reducing on this run (depth → 150m ⁻¹) as going A → B & confirmed on LIDAR [depth noisy on this run]
					Some turbulence (RH) - probably dry convective elements within well mixed layer here.
111035	END R3.1	4000'			At Pt B.
111111	START P3.1	4000'	119°		Start P3.1 to 2500', then 1200', 1000'/mi.
					Wind 260°/8kt.
111240	Turn P3	2500'			Alt. 2500' hold, turn into reciprocal
111443	Restart P3	2500' ↓	326°		Restart P3, heading for Pt-B.
111701	END P3 START R4.1	1200'	326°		B → A; ALICE/SWS looking at THIS run.
1122					Neph values N 150 m ⁻¹ along THIS run (50°, 220kt)
112430					HEIMAN 50-55° surface temp last 45 mins
112520					Neph values ↑ > 200 m ⁻¹ now as head towards A.
112938	END P4.1	1200'	344°		At Pt-A
					Ascend to 1800' for 1 st 50 orbit

Mission Scientist's Log

K³

Flight No **B448** Date 9-5-09 Name JK Page 4 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
113035	ORBIT 1	1800'	040°		START ORBIT 1 (50°) ↻
113154	ORBIT 01		090°		END
113252	02		090°		↻ START ORBIT 2 (not kept by SWS)
113311	02 <i>abundant</i>				head back to 'A'
113425	START R4.2	1200'	160°	}	START R4.2 A → B
					aries / SWS looking upwards
114300			→		Neph values 200/150 m ⁻¹ as landing S. & L ₂ level being less aerosol too.
114550					Neph values steady at 140-150 m ⁻¹ .
114635	END R4.2	1200'			END R4.2 Climb to 1800' for next orbit at B
114729	START ORBIT 2	1800'	140°	}	Orbit 2
114846	END 02	1800'	140°		descend to 1200', towards B
115110	START R4.3	1200'	345°	}	Start R4.3, B → A
					aries / SWS ↓
115910					Wind 315° / SKT: (VEGIE DIL ^u), Thicker Aerosol again as heading N.
120406	END R4.3	1200'	349°		END LAST R4.2 1200' At A Will Profile ↑ to 16000' next
120547	START P4.1	1200'	169°		A → B; Profile 1000'/min
121620	END P4.1	16000'			NO AEROSOL HERE, will ↓ to 12000' to be in top of aerosol/dust
121962	START R5.1	12000' (2120)	345°	}	B → A; in top of aerosol layer
					Wet Neph to 40 m ⁻¹ (VISUALLY + can't keep up)
1226			←		Wind 025° / 30kft depth ↑ to 80 m ⁻¹

MARS
CAMERAS
FILTERS

Mission Scientist's Log

ETA 1325#
HW PS 1003

Flight No **B448** Date 9-5-09 Name DEK Page 5 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
122900					Nepl values ↑ to ~105 m ⁻¹ max.
123005	RS.1	FL120, 12000'	347°		WIND 030°/28KT
123130	END RS.1				END RS.1 ↓ A, turning ↓
123333	P6 ↑	FLDP 12000'	182°		Commence P6
123532	END P6 / START R	12000' (FL150)	159°		END P6 / START R A → B ABOVE DUST
123910		Above Aerosol / Dust. ↓			Nepl values 30 ↓ now ~15 m ⁻¹ (start run) CLEAR SKIES ABOVE THIS H2
124253	END R.S.1	FL150			END R.S.1 ABOVE AEROSOL LAYER
124437	START P7	FL150 ↑	020°		START FINAL PROFILE FL150 / FL210 OUT OF AREA
124855	END P7	FL210	016°	21.6W 56.30N	
1333					LAND MUSCAT (R/W OS)
0842					
4:51m					
1339			240°		START PIRANETTE
1341			240°		END PIRANETTE.
	*	END	MEVEX	DETACHMENT	*

B448-#mevexViRClog

```
*** Opened channel log for #mevex at 09/05/2009 10:04:54
[2009/05/09 10:04] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.202) has joined #mevex
[2009/05/09 10:06] [FAAMOpsDetach] How now?
[2009/05/09 10:09] [FAAMOpsDetach] Where did you download Dave's aircraft photos to?
[2009/05/09 10:11] <FAAM_flt_man> are, someone there
[2009/05/09 10:11] <FAAM_flt_man> my PC
[2009/05/09 10:11] [FAAMOpsDetach] is it accessible from the masirah?
[2009/05/09 10:12] <FAAM_flt_man> I can't remember, tell the truth
[2009/05/09 10:12] <FAAM_flt_man> if it's in the masirah, I was sat in the corner nr the door
[2009/05/09 10:12] <MetODaveP> No worries, I'll grab them some other time
[2009/05/09 10:13] <MetODaveP> Is Kindred having another charmed flight?
[2009/05/09 10:14] <FAAM_flt_man> well, it depends what you mean by charmed
[2009/05/09 10:14] <FAAM_flt_man> but no big thrusting peaks of dust
[2009/05/09 10:15] <MetODaveP> Some dust though I hope
[2009/05/09 10:19] <FAAM_flt_man> yes, we are profiling through FL090 ish where we find a narrow
    band of dust (~60 - 70/m)
[2009/05/09 10:21] <MetODaveP> I didn't think he got out of bed for anything less than 500/m
    anymore!
[2009/05/09 10:21] <MetODaveP> Good to have a contrast to the last flight in that area though
[2009/05/09 10:23] <FAAM_flt_man> FL085, up to 160/m
[2009/05/09 10:24] <MetODaveP> SEVIRI derived AOD somewhere between 0.5 and 0.8 in your area ATM
[2009/05/09 10:50] [FAAMOpsDetach] Message for Martin G (from Ian) - does he want the SWS/SMIMS off
    for calibration when the aircraft returns to Cranfield?
[2009/05/09 10:52] <FAAM_flt_man> do u mean the whole rack?
[2009/05/09 10:57] [FAAMOpsDetach] it doesn't say in the email but it sounds like the whole rack,
    does Martin not know?
[2009/05/09 10:58] <FAAM_flt_man> not a good time to ask him.....
[2009/05/09 10:58] *** MetODaveP (~dfpollard@85.154.2.202) has quit IRC [Ping timeout: 240 seconds]
[2009/05/09 11:01] <FAAM_flt_man> busy sws period
[2009/05/09 11:14] <FAAM_flt_man> i've got a banana
[2009/05/09 11:34] *** FAAM_flt_man (~GLUXE@203.38.13.31) has quit IRC [Read error: Connection
    reset by peer]
[2009/05/09 11:34] [FAAMOpsDetach] best keep it
[2009/05/09 11:54] *** FAAM_flt_man (~GLUXE@203.38.13.36) has joined #mevex
[2009/05/09 11:54] <FAAM_flt_man> roasting
[2009/05/09 11:58] [FAAMOpsDetach] what, the banana. I prefer it with a butter glaze
[2009/05/09 11:59] <FAAM_flt_man> low level - lots of turb and heat!
[2009/05/09 12:00] [FAAMOpsDetach] all bearing up?
[2009/05/09 12:00] <FAAM_flt_man> mostly
[2009/05/09 12:02] <FAAM_flt_man> playing hell with my wind problem
[2009/05/09 12:02] [FAAMOpsDetach] ...and the coin rash?
[2009/05/09 12:03] <FAAM_flt_man> flaring up
[2009/05/09 12:03] <FAAM_flt_man> gone from small change to 50p's
[2009/05/09 12:04] [FAAMOpsDetach] any sign of chives?
[2009/05/09 12:07] <FAAM_flt_man> dont know what u mean
[2009/05/09 12:08] [FAAMOpsDetach] rhymes with egg
[2009/05/09 12:08] <FAAM_flt_man> nothing rhymes with egg
[2009/05/09 12:09] [FAAMOpsDetach] ...or smells like it
[2009/05/09 12:10] [FAAMOpsDetach] are you sticking to the plan or is there likely to be an added
    extra interesting layer or 3?
[2009/05/09 12:11] <FAAM_flt_man> we're following the spirit of the plan fairly well
[2009/05/09 12:12] [FAAMOpsDetach] ETA?
[2009/05/09 12:12] <FAAM_flt_man> no thanks
[2009/05/09 12:13] <FAAM_flt_man> capt's in the cludgy
[2009/05/09 12:13] [FAAMOpsDetach] ask the co, he'll know
[2009/05/09 12:26] [FAAMOpsDetach] well, he is surely out of the cludgy by now
[2009/05/09 12:29] <FAAM_flt_man> firrst stab of 1345Z for the ETA
[2009/05/09 12:37] [FAAMOpsDetach] okay
[2009/05/09 12:50] <FAAM_flt_man> new ETA, 1335Z
[2009/05/09 12:58] [FAAMOpsDetach] broadcast to dflops
[2009/05/09 12:59] <FAAM_flt_man> super
[2009/05/09 12:59] <FAAM_flt_man> top-tastic
[2009/05/09 13:04] [FAAMOpsDetach] excitement levels today on a score of 1 to 8.7?
[2009/05/09 13:04] <FAAM_flt_man> i'd say a 5,3
[2009/05/09 13:05] [FAAMOpsDetach] a whisker off buoyant then
[2009/05/09 13:09] [FAAMOpsDetach] Okay,
[2009/05/09 13:10] [FAAMOpsDetach] I'm heading awf to bring the car out, see y'all soon
[2009/05/09 13:10] [FAAMOpsDetach] thnax, mop
[2009/05/09 13:12] *** FAAM_flt_man (~GLUXE@203.38.13.36) has quit IRC
*** Closed channel log for #mevex at 09/05/2009 13:14:21
```

Cloud Physics Flight Log B448

Date:9/05/09	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 06:30:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	AUX1 Time: +0	AUX2 Time: +0
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DAU2 Disk space?

	PCASP SPP-200		CDP		PCASP		2DC		FFSSP		SID3	
Operated?					No						No	
Pre-flight checks	Vref	7.41	Ref V (~3):	1.71	Vref (>7):		El#1 V (>1):	-1.4	Ref V:	3.3	Comms?	No
	Sample flow	1.13			Flow (~1):		El#32 V (>1):	-1.4				
	Sheath flow	15.2			Pressure:							
					Temp (NDIT)							

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
08:59:00	FL230												Heaters on
09:22:01	FL260												Start Run 1.1
09:23:00				30	0.2						4		
09:25:00				30	0.2								
09:27:00				30	0.2								
09:29:00				30	0.2								
09:31:00				30	0.2								
09:33:00				25	0.2								
09:34:40													End Run
09:42:47	FL260												Start Run 1.2
09:43:00				25	0.2								
09:45:00				25	0.2								
09:47:00				25	0.2								
09:49:00				25	0.2								
09:51:00				30	0.2								
09:53:00													End of Run
09:59:34	FL260			30	0.2						5		Start Profile 1
10:00:18	FL250			30	0.2								
10:00:48	FL240			30	0.2								
10:01:18	FL230			30	0.2								
10:02:12	FL220			30	0.2								
10:03:09	FL210			30	0.2								
10:04:15	FL200			30	0.2								

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
10:05:22	FL190	0.05	1	30	0.5								
10:06:35	FL180	0.05	2	35	1								
10:07:27	FL170	0.05	2	45	1								
10:08:25	FL160	0.05	2	45	1								
10:12:11	FL150	0.05	2	40	1						6		
10:13:34	FL140	0.1	4	100	1								
10:14:51	FL130	0.1	5	130	1								
10:16:10	FL120	0.1	5	250	1.5								
10:17:49	FL110	0.1	5	200	1.5								
10:19:50	FL100	0.5	5	300	1.5								
10:21:24	FL090	0.4	5	500	2						7		
10:23:02	8000'	0.4	5	500	2						8		
10:25:55	8000'												Start Run 2.1
10:26:00		0.5	10	600	2						9		
10:28:00		0.4	10	500	2						10		
10:30:00		0.6	10	400	2						12		
10:32:00		0.6	10	350	2						13		
10:34:00		0.45	10	300	2						14		Heaters off
10:36:00		0.4	10	300	2								
10:38:00		0.4	10	350	2								
10:38:40													End of Run
10:40:29	8000'												Start Run 2.2
10:41:00		0.5	10	400	2						15		
10:43:00		0.5	10	400	2								
10:45:00		0.5	10	300	2						16		
10:47:00		0.4	7	300	2								
10:49:00		0.4	7	450	2						17		
10:51:00		0.5	10	500	2								
10:52:35	8000'	0.6	10	600	2								End of Run & Start Profile 2
10:53:48	7000'	0.8	7	800	2						18		
10:54:55	6000'	0.8	7	750	2						19		
10:57:59	5000'	0.9	7	800	2						20		
10:58:48	4000'												End of Profile & Start Run 3.1
10:59:00		0.8	7	600	2						21		
11:01:00		0.8	7	600	2								
11:03:00		0.8	7	550	2			0.5			22		

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
11:05:00		0.6	7	500	2			0.5			23		
11:07:00		0.6	7	500	2			0.5			24		
11:09:00		0.6	7	500	2			1			25		
11:10:35													End of Run
11:11:08	4000'												Start Profile 3
11:12:20	3000'	0.6	7	400	2			0.5			26		
11:15:17	2000'	0.5	7	450	2						27		
11:17:04	1200'												End of Profile & Start Run 4.1
11:18:00		0.5	7	450	2			0.5			28		
11:20:00		0.5	7	400	2			0.5			29		
11:22:00		0.5	7	450	2			0.5			30		
11:24:00		0.5	7	450	2						31		
11:26:00		0.5	7	500	2						32		
11:28:00		0.5	7	550	2						33		
11:29:39													End of Run
11:30:38	1800'												Start Orbit
11:33:08													End of Orbits
11:34:16	1200'												Start Run 4.2
11:35:00		0.5	7	550	2			0.5			37		
11:37:00		0.5	7	500	2						38		
11:39:00		0.5	7	500	2			0.5			39		
11:41:00		0.5	7	400	2			0.5			40		
11:43:00		0.5	7	400	2			0.5					
11:45:00		0.5	7	400	2			0.5			41		
11:46:36													End of Run
11:47:29	1800'												Start Orbit
11:48:47													End Orbit
11:51:12	1200'												Start Run 4.3
11:52:00		0.4	7	400	2			0.5			43		
11:54:00		0.4	7	400	2			0.5			44		
11:56:00		0.4	7	400	2						45		
11:58:00		0.5	7	400	2						46		
12:00:00		0.5	7	450	2			0.5			47		
12:02:00		0.6	7	500	2						48		
12:04:06													End of Run
12:05:39	1200'												Start Profile 4

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
12:06:07	FL020	0.6	7	500	2						51		
12:07:10	FL030	0.6	7	500	2								
12:07:59	FL040	0.6	7	500	2						52		
12:08:52	FL050	0.6	7	450	2								
12:09:38	FL060	0.6	7	450	2						53		
12:10:32	FL070	0.6	7	500	2								
12:11:10	FL080	0.7	7	400	2								
12:11:52	FL090	0.7	7	400	2						54		
12:12:34	FL100	0.7	7	350	2								
12:13:12	FL110	0.7	7	300	2								
12:13:56	FL120	0.2	5	150	1.5								
12:14:38	FL130	0.2	5	150	1.5								
12:15:30	FL140	0.2	5	100	1								Heaters on
12:16:08	FL150	0.1	2	100	1								
12:16:24	FL157	0.1	1	50	1								End of Profile Start Profile 5
12:17:27	FL150	0.1	2	100	1								
12:18:11	FL140	0.2	2	130	1								
12:18:51	FL130	0.2	2	150	1								
12:19:52	FL120												End of Profile & Start Run 5.1
12:20:00		0.2	2	150	1								
12:22:00		0.2	5	200	1.5								
12:24:00		0.2	5	175	2						55		
12:26:00		0.2	5	200	2								
12:28:00		0.2	5	200	2								
12:30:00		0.3	5	350	2						56		
12:31:31													End of Run
12:33:28	FL120												Start Profile 6
12:34:06	FL130	0.2	3	200	2								
12:34:50	FL140	0.2	3	200	2						57		
12:35:33	FL150												End of Profile & Start Run 6.1
12:36:00		0.1	3	100	1								
12:38:00		0.1	3	100	1								
12:40:00		0.1	3	80	1								
12:42:00		0.1	3	100	1								
12:42:53													End of Run
12:44:37	FL150												Start Profile 7

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No: **B448**

Date: **09-05-2009**

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 μm pore size)	Bottom inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 μm pore size)
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Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run1	B448-N52	----	----	Top					Blanks (FL 260)
Filters run1	B448-N53	----	----	Bottom					
Filters run 2	B448-N54	----	----	Top	10:26:34	10:50:34		620	8000 ft
Filters run 2	B448-N55	----	----	Bottom	10:26:34	10:50:34		569	
Filters run 3	B448-N56	----	----	Top	11:00:16	11:10:16		358	400ft
Filters run 3	B448-N57	----	----	Bottom	11:00:16	11:10:16		327	
Filters run 4	B448-N58	----	----	Top	11:15:25	12:34:25		1	No sampling (system was closed but V _{bottom} was still increasing...)
Filters run 4	B448-N59	----	----	Bottom	11:15:25	12:34:25		643	

Flight:

B448

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problem

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B448

Date: 09 May 2009

Instruments

UFC – upward camera nor recorded (damaged cable), replaced by IR spotter camera which was not recorded due to AGC problems with camera

AMTG – lost LCD

SID3 not operated

CPC – u/s, not operated.

BBRs – Lower Pyrgeometer data rubbish. Upper noisy start of flight, then ok

IR cameras – problems with LW & MW cameras pre-flight

Cloud Physics

new pcasp noise from SWS 28V ?

Nevzorov; failed sensor, not operated

Chemistry –

MARSS – “double bounce” at start of flight due to high temperatures on the ground. Better as flight progressed.

Filters – flow v. poor, pump suspected. Flow in one line virtually non-existent later in flight

SATCOM-H: mpds service good

Aircraft

Overhead panel fell during t/o in posn before core consoles, port-side

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

ARIES flight log

Flight: B 448 page 1 of 3

Date: 09 May 09 Operator(s): S. ROGERS Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: MEVEX: Dust

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
~0700	—						Power on OK. @0858
~0845	TAKE OFF						CoB running? Window 41C mirror 26C
09 0611	FL260	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal macro
09 0735	"	60x1	Z	0	82	42	Zenith
09 08—	"	360x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir clear above
09 1141	"	Nad 3min	N	0	81	41	Nadir 3 minute macro. Sandes
09 2800	"	80x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
09 2836	"	N 3min	N	0	81	41	Nadir 3 minute. A-train @0947Z
09 3741	FL260	N 3min	N	0	81	41	Nadir 3min Sandes
10 2505	8000'	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal ↓
10 2625	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir Very bumpy
10 2814	"	240x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith. Very hazy outside. Can barely see the ground.
10 3037	"	240x1	N	0	81	40	
10 3140	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	
10 3303	"	240x1	Z	0	81	41	
10 3515	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	
10 3727	"	240x1	Z	0	81	41	
10 3841	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	↓
10 4023	8000'	cal	CH	0	81	42	
10 4148	"	240x1	N	0	81	42	
10 4245	"	240x1	Z	0	81	41	
10 4455	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	Surface more visible than earlier.
10 4725	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	
10 4847	"	240x1	Z	0	81	41	
10 4943	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	
10 5150	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	↑
10 5240	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	
10 5344	↓ 7000'	cal	CH	0	81	41	
10 5311	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	
10 5333	4000'	240x1	Z	0	81	42	Still bumpy.
11 0115	"	240x1	N	0	81	42	

ARIES flight log

Flight: 13448

page 2 of 3

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
11 0334	4000'	240x1	Z	0	81	41	
11 0459	"	cal	CH	0	81	42	
11 0623	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	Skill bump Send dunes below Some variation in sand colour.
11 0830	"	240x1	Z	0	81	42	
11 1031	"	cal	CH	0	81	42	
11 1640	1400'	N3min	N	0	81	43	Surface clearly visible. Either its jinking around or we are. Bumpy
11 2506	"	cal	CH	0	81	47	
11 2944		360x1	Z				aborted
11 3039	1500'	360x1	Z				Orbit 50° right
11 3135		cal	CH	0			aborted due to unexpected orbit
11 3312		cal	CH	0			
11 3928	1400'	360x1	Z	0	81	50	
11 3731	"	23min	Z	0	81	50	Bumpy
11 4520	"	cal	CH	0	81	51	
11 4732	1500'	360x1	Z	0	81	52	Orbit 45° right
11 4852	"	cal	CH	0	81	52	Hot.
11 5023	1200'	360x1	N	0	81	52	Bumpy. My hate for Mr. Gled knows no bounds.
11 5325	"	N3min	N	0	81	52	Window 42 C. mirror 46 C.
12 0411	"	cal	CH	0	81	53	
12 1913	FL120	cal	CH	0	81	48	CBB still cooling after change in altitude
12 2039	"	360x1	N	0	81	48	
12 2338	"	120x1	Z	0	81	45	
12 25	"	cal	CH	0	81	45	
12 2620	"	240x1	N	0	81	44	
12 2832	"	120x1	Z	0	81	42	
12 2935	"	cal	CH	0	81	42	
12 3054	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	
12 3137	"	cal	CH	0	81	42	
12 3859	FL150	cal	CH	0	81	41	
12 3717	"	360x1	N	0	81	41	
12 4022	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	09/05/09	Flight	B448	log pages
Operator(s)	Rob King		Campaign	MEVEX		
Departure			Arrival			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on					at time	0715
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	42°C	Ch	42°C	Ch18	37°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on					at time	0715
Initial target temperatures	Hot	315	Cold	323		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)					at time	
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual	

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software					at time	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						•
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual	
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time			
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot				Cold
	Deimos:	Hot				Cold
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						•
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						•
System running again					at time	

Flight B448 09:02:32

Heading 208 deg Speed 338 knots Height 25.2kft Press 372mb

Lat 22°24.0'N Long 57°30.0'E Wind 9 ms-1/ 338 deg

Temp -23.03C Dewpoint -39.8C

From start to now

Current values		
----- STATIC PRESSURE	372.65	mb
++++ DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-23.04	deg C
++++ DEW POINT	-39.81	deg C

CLIMB OUT OF MISCAT

NOTE: SUPER ADIABATIC &
STRONG HYDROLAPSE
FROM SURFACE.

& WELL MIXED ABOVE

D20090509_092510.2 082029174 none, none

D20090509_094259.3 082119154 none, none

Flight B448 09:02:13

Heading 209 deg Speed 337 knots Height 25.0kft Press 374mb

Lat 22°24.0'N Long 57°30.0'E Wind 9 ms-1/ 326 deg

Temp -22.71C Dewpoint -39.02C

From start to now

Current values			
	PRESSURE HEIGHT	25.08	Kft
•••••	NEPH BLUE SP	3.49	m-1
•••••	NEPH GREEN SP	4.13	m-1
•••••	NEPH RED SP	-0.88	m-1

Flight B448 12:00:39

Heading 342 deg Speed 225 knots Height 1.3kft Press 963mb

Lat 21°12.0'N Long 56°0.0'E Wind 2 ms-1/ 322 deg

Temp 40.13C Dewpoint 4.5C

From start to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	963.51	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	40.14	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	4.5	deg C

CLIMB OUT OF MUSCAT

← PROFILES P1 → P3 IN SURVEY AREA.

New plot, same times

Flight B448 12:01:03

Heading 344 deg Speed 227 knots Height 1.3kft Press 964mb

Lat 21°18.0'N Long 56°0.0'E Wind 1 ms-1/ 336 deg

Temp 40.45C Dewpoint 3.99C

From start to now

Current values			
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	43263	secs	<input checked="" type="radio"/> All
NEPH BLUE SP	198.52	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
NEPH GREEN SP	199.49	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
NEPH RED SP	213.07	m-1	<input type="radio"/>

NEPH vs TIME

First part of SCATIE (1st of 2nd
NEX)

New plot, same times

Flight B448 12:54:21

Heading 15 deg Speed 312 knots Height 21.0kft Press 446mb

Lat 21°30.0'N Long 56°30.0'E Wind 12 ms-1/ 12 deg

Temp -12.19C Dewpoint -25.55C

From 11:47:22 to now

Current values			
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	46461	secs	<input checked="" type="radio"/> All
NEPH BLUE SP	1.06	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
NEPH GREEN SP	1.47	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
NEPH RED SP	1.43	m-1	<input type="radio"/>

NEPH vs TIME

ORBIT 2, Alt 4.3 XT 1200', Runs 5.1 (FL120) &
6.1 (FL150).
Profiles P4 → P7,

B

Flight B448 12:54:33

Heading 15 deg Speed 313 knots Height 21.0kft Press 446mb

Lat 21°30.0'N Long 56°30.0'E Wind 12 ms-1/ 12 deg

Temp -12.21C Dewpoint -26.66C

From start to now

Current values		
GIN LONGITUDE	56.57	deg (+ve E)
GIN LATITUDE	21.55	deg (+ve N)

Flight B448 12:54:51

Heading 15 deg Speed 312 knots Height 21.0kft Press 446mb

Lat 21°30.0'N Long 56°30.0'E Wind 12 ms-1/ 13 deg

Temp -12.2C Dewpoint -28.34C

From start to now

Current values			
●	PRESSURE HEIGHT	21.01	Kft
●	NEPH BLUE SP	1.9	m-1
●	NEPH GREEN SP	3.58	m-1
●	NEPH RED SP	2.11	m-1

NEPH VS HEIGHT (WHOLE FLIGHT,
EXCEPT RETURN TRANSIT)

Flight B448 12:55:05

Heading 15 deg Speed 311 knots Height 21.0kft Press 446mb

Lat 21°30.0'N Long 56°30.0'E Wind 12 ms-1/ 12 deg

Temp -12.22C Dewpoint -28.49C

From 11:37:30 to now

Current values
 +-----+ STATIC PRESSURE 446.13 mb
 +-----+ DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP -12.23 deg C
 +-----+ DEW POINT -28.5 deg C

Profile P4 → P7 Together
 (T/O ^{LATTER PART} and of SURFACE IN AREA 3
 WITH RWS AT FL120 & FL150)

Number of profiles

PROFILE DESCENT P1

CALIPSO 2009/05/09 UTC CALIPSO ORBITAL PREDICT PLOT EPOCH DATE: 09/05/08
■ lat: 22.52 lon: 57.16 res: 9 km

Southern Asia CAM Aerosol Optical Depth
At 09Z on 9/05/2009, from 00Z on 8/05/2009

AOD T+033

Southern Asia CAM Dust Concentrations
At 09Z on 9/05/2009, from 00Z on 8/05/2009

Dust concentration (log3) T+033

Southern Asia CAM Cloud
At 09Z on 9/05/2009, from 00Z on 8/05/2009

Total Cloud Cover T+033

Met Office Southern Asia CAM Dust Concentr
At 12Z on09/05/2009, from 00Z on08/05,

Surface dust concentration T+36

2000–5000ft

g m^{-3}

1e-5 1e-4 0.001 0.01 0.1

1e-5 1e-4

Met Office Southern Asia CAM Aerosol Optical
At 12Z on09/05/2009, from 00Z on08/05/

AOD T+36

0.05 0.1 0.2 0.4 0.8 1.6